

Designing an Emotional Experience for Product Sounds

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conference theme: Senses/methods

Abstract

A method is presented to analyze and determine the relevant features of product sounds. Although the method is still under development it has been successfully applied in sound design projects for industry (Philips, Procter and Gamble) and in student projects (some in collaboration with industry). In this presentation, I will discuss the problems that one encounters in the design of product sounds and how these sounds can be analyzed. In addition, examples will be shown in which sounds were effectively altered to evoke specific emotional experiences, associated meanings, and functional feedback.

Introduction

Most of our domestic appliances make sound. Everybody has been irritated by the sound of a vacuum cleaner, excited by the finishing sound of a drip filter coffeemaker, or warned by the alarm bell of a microwave oven. In general, a distinction can be made between consequential and synthetic or digitized sounds (also named intentional sounds). Consequential sounds are sounds that result from our interaction with products and are dependent on how an appliance has been constructed. For example, a toothbrush will make a certain sound dependent on the type of engine (the rpm) and the gears that have been used. Synthetic or digitized sounds are mostly used in user-interfaces or as alarm signals. In this paper I will focus on consequential sounds.

People often use the feedback of these sounds unconsciously and associate specific experiential aspects to them. For example, one hears how the brewing process of a drip filter coffeemaker develops over time, or one hears if the bag of a vacuum cleaner is full, or when the battery of a toothbrush runs out. In addition, product sounds may evoke more basic or cognitive/evaluative emotions (Van Egmond, Desmet, & van der Helm, 2004) but also they may transmit a brand image or convey an associated meaning (Özcan & Van Egmond, 2005).

Sound quality and its constituents have been studied to some extent and the important role of perception has been indicated (e.g., Blauert & Jekosch, 1997; Bodden, 2000; Lyon, 2003). In addition, the affective evaluation and the experience of sound have been studied in relation to sound quality (Vastfjall, Gulbol, Kleiner, & Garling, 2002). This latter paper emphasizes the important distinction between the evaluation of the sound as it is, and the affective experience a sound evokes in a person. Based on these perceptual aspects methodologies have been proposed or can be derived that deal with the quality and the design of sounds. (Blauert & Jekosch, 1997; Buss, Schulte-Fortkamp & Muckel, 2000; Lyon, 2003). In this paper a methodology is presented that has been used at the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering.

One of the main problems in the design of a sound of a domestic appliance is the identification of the relevant perceptual features in the sound. If these features are identified the next step is to manipulate them and to determine the effect on our emotional experience. The identification of these features is complex because product sounds are “noisy”. If a sound is “noisy” it contains a lot of randomness in its spectral and temporal composition. In general, any randomness is difficult to model. However, domestic appliances often contain

engines (causing periodicity) or construction features that due to their vibration and resonance properties (filtering the sound) change the spectral properties in such a way that the sounds do not have a completely random structure.

Perceptual Domains of Sound

The hearing area of humans ranges from 20 Hz-20kHz in the frequency domain and in the loudness domain from the threshold in quiet (0Db) and the threshold of pain (120Db and up) (see, e.g., Zwicker & Fastl, 1990). In this hearing area speech and music are two well-studied perceptual domains. The perceptual domain of music encompasses the perceptual domain of speech in the hearing area. In other words, the perceptual domain of music is larger than that of speech. If we consider only the spectral structure of speech and music, timbre (sound color) is the perceptual attribute by which musical instruments and speech vowels can be distinguished.

Each natural sound consists of a series of overtones (sinusoids). Pitch producing instruments can be characterized by the overtone structure and the amplitude variations of these overtones. In Figure 1 the spectrogram of a C6 Piano tone is shown. Frequency (y-axis) is presented as a function of time (x-axis). The amplitude of the overtones is represented by grey scale values. It can be seen that there is periodicity in the overtone structure of the tone. Only a limited number of tones are present and are related by a harmonic series (with small deviations from this series, called inharmonicity). In addition, it can be seen that the overtones with a low frequency are higher in intensity and are sustained over a longer period of time. Most sounds produced by musical instruments show similar structural aspects. These sounds are often used in feedback or as alarm sounds. In the next paragraph the perceptual domain of product sounds is discussed.

Figure 1. Spectrogram of a piano tone (C6). X-axis represents the time in seconds. Y-axis represents the frequency in Hz. Grey-scale is used to indicate intensity.

Product Sounds

Product sounds differ considerably in their complexity due to different operating cycles or product user interactions. These aspects affect both the spectral and temporal components of the sound. We can distinguish between appliances that consist of *autonomous*, of *partly autonomous*, and of *user dependent* control systems. These different control systems will affect the repeatability of similar sound events and thus will affect the possibility of making proper predictions concerning experiential aspects.

An example of an *autonomous* product would be the central heating system in our houses or any system with its own control system. The heating kettle will turn on and let the pump run. There is no direct user involvement because the product has its own control system. An example of *partly autonomous* systems is a coffeemaker or a washing machine. In case of coffeemaker one has to put in the coffee, the water, place a cup or a coffeepot, and switch the coffeemaker on. These usage actions will not be the same every time and thus the sound events related to these actions are not similar. A *user dependent* control system is, for example, an electrical toothbrush. In this case two types of sound production can be distinguished: 1. The product is turned on and not used, resulting is a stationary sound; 2 The product is turned on and used, the sound changes under the influences of user actions (i.c. the

electrical toothbrush, pressure and movement). In the latter case, it will be more difficult to design the sound because the spectral composition and temporal organization of the sound will change dependent on individual usage actions. It is, however, possible to determine the boundaries in which these fluctuations of spectral composition and temporal organization occur. The difficulty is to position a sound design solution within these boundaries so that it complies to the experience one wants to evoke.

It could be argued that a stationary sound production will not happen and it is therefore unnecessary to make the aforementioned distinction. However, for companies this distinction maybe important. Consumers that want to buy a new product often switch it on in a shop. Recently, Procter and Gamble has designed and patented packaging (e.g., for the crest tooth brush) that allows potential buyers to switch it on. The product then, of course, makes a sound that will be a very important carrier of experiential and brand values. It is therefore essential that the stationary sound is designed and complies to the wanted brand values. In conclusion, the type of interaction with the product already influences the variability of the spectral and temporal composition of a product sound. Consequently, this variability limits the possibility to design a consequential sound based on the required experiential properties.

Spectral and temporal structure of product sounds

In previous research, we distinguished between structural features in the temporal domain and structural features in the spectral domain (Özcan & Van Egmond, submitted). The presence of these structural features is an important factor in the memory for product sound categories. In designing sounds for products these structural features can be systematically manipulated and yield a consistent prediction of how they affect the emotional experience. In Figure 2, the spectrogram of an alarm clock sound is presented (time, x-axis; frequency, y-axis; and grayscale to indicate the intensity of frequencies). This sound is highly structured in the temporal domain (silence lasts 0.2 seconds between beeps and the duration of the beep lasts 0.3 seconds) and in the spectral domain (periodicity between the overtones). Because of the structural aspects in this sound it can be more easily redesigned or modified (it is, of course, not a consequential sound).

Figure 2. The spectrogram of an alarm clock.

In Figure 3 the spectrogram of an electrical toothbrush is shown. It can be readily seen that there is more noise in this sound. In addition, the rpm of the engine generates periodic aspect in the spectrum. The sound is rather constant over time but it changes around 2.2 seconds because of the pressure on the brush. In this case, the perceived pitch increases. If the pressure is varied systematically the boundaries of this variation can be determined and a sound concept can be proposed that incorporates this variability.

Figure 3. A spectrogram of an electrical toothbrush.

In Figure 4 the spectrogram of a vacuumcleaner is presented. It can be readily seen that due to the amount of noise in the temporal and spectral domain structural aspects are difficult to derive, which makes it more difficult to change the sound in terms of experiential aspects.

Figure 4. The spectrogram of a vacuumcleaner.

Thus, the sound producing parts and the interaction of a user with a product presents us with constraints in the design of a product sound on the basis of a wanted emotional experience. In addition, product sounds consist of a lot of randomness in the spectral and temporal domain (noisiness). This makes it more difficult to derive the structural aspects related to the emotional experience. Consequently, it will be more difficult to design a proper sound. Before describing the procedural aspects of the methodology the process of auditory perception needs to be (briefly) considered.

Process of Auditory Perception

It may be hypothesized that bottom-up and top-down processes contribute to specific aspects of auditory perception. Psychoacoustical measures that contribute to the sensory pleasantness of sounds may be considered as stemming from the bottom-up process. These measures will not be influenced by top-down driven knowledge like schemata, associations of meaning or more evaluative/cognitive-based emotional experiences. Zwicker & Fastl (1990) proposed a psychoacoustical model for sensory pleasantness that consists of a weighted sum of loudness, sharpness, roughness, tonalness¹. Increases in loudness, sharpness, and roughness result in a decrease in sensory pleasantness whereas an increase in tonalness results in an increase of sensory pleasantness. Sensory pleasantness is a “bottom-up measure” that may evoke more basic type of emotions as fear or pain. These basic emotions are often not the emotions one wants to manipulate when one conceptualizes a product experience consisting of a mix of more evaluative emotions and brand values. These latter aspects require top-down driven knowledge in the evaluation of the sounds. A challenge in sound design is to limit the negative impact of the bottom-up driven features in order to be able to design a sound based on higher level experiential aspects (e.g., brand values). An example of this would be not only to design the sound of a coffeemaker but to design the brewing experience of the sound of a coffeemaker on the basis of an indication when certain sound events in time should occur. One could compare this with the design of the music for a movie.

Methodology for Consequential Product Sound Analysis and Design

As stated before to improve product sounds knowledge and techniques of different disciplines (acoustics, psychoacoustics, psychology, engineering) have to be employed. Four main stages

¹They use tonality, but I find this term too much associated with tonality in music perception.

constitute the methodology: Recording; Analysis; Design; Testing. The order of the last three stages can be varied and can be recursively applied depending on the problem addressed.

Recording

The quality of and the positioning of the microphone are—as in all recordings—important issues that have an effect not only on the quality of the recording but may also affect the spectral composition of the recorded sound and consequently may emphasize perceptual features one normally does not hear. For example, one can imagine that putting a microphone in front of the air outlet of a hair dryer will yield a different recording than putting a microphone on the side. In addition, the recording has to be accompanied with a measurement by a sound level pressure meter to know the loudness level at the time of the recording (we use Bruel & Kjaer Type 2260 measurement equipment). Several recordings will be made of an appliance. The appliance will be recorded with and without usage actions (as mentioned before the sound changes when some appliances are used, e.g., toothbrush) and the appliance will be deconstructed to record the important sound producing parts separately. The latter enables us to relate specific spectral features to a source and if a new sound is synthesized to use different recordings of other sound producing parts. For example, one could think of recordings of different pumps (centrifugal or plunger).

Analysis

The first step in the analysis phase is to analyze the sounds on its spectral-temporal features in combination with our own perception and the sound producing parts in the appliance. In Figure 5, the time amplitude and the spectrogram of the recording of a coffeemaker is shown (examples stem from a MSc thesis from Van Balken, 2001). The top graph shows a normalized amplitude as a function of time. The bottom graph shows the frequency (intensity indicated in terms of grey scale) as a function of time. The sound producing parts are presented in both graphs in addition to a perceptual event (squeaking that stands out). In the top graph the valve ticking are blown up because these events are perceptually very salient.

Figure 5. The sound of a coffeemaker represented in a time-amplitude and in a time-frequency/intensity domain.

In Table 1 the sound is represented as a function of sound producing product parts and use stages. This type of inventory helps to communicate between engineers and sound designers to relate specific sound experiences back to the construction. In the spectrogram of Figure 5 it can be seen that the squeaking (approximately 82 seconds) caused by the “Air driven through the hole in the pad holder” produces a frequencies with an a relatively high intensity (black line) for the higher frequency. This squeaking is an unpleasant sound, and is one of the aspects one would improve. In addition, it can be seen in the spectrogram that the pump starts quite sudden resulting in frequency of a relatively high intensity across the entire frequency domain. This sound is also a unpleasant sound.

<i>Sound</i>	<i>Sound Producing Product Parts</i>	<i>Use stage</i>
squeaking	Metal opening system	Opening lid
sucking	Air escaping valve for the reservoir	Placing the reservoir
rustling	Boiler	Heating
ticking	Valves between boiler and spout	Heating
whirring	Pump	Brewing
squeaking	Air driven through the hole in pad holder	Brewing
rustling	Brew chamber	Brewing
coffee flow	Spout	Brewing
rustling	Boiler	Post-Brewing

Table 1. Characteristic coffemaker sounds with related product parts and use stages

The next step is the determination of psychoacoustical attributes as, for example, roughness, sharpness, and loudness. This analysis is performed by implemented algorithms but in addition by subjective scaling measures. Especially, implementations of roughness algorithms do not seem to predict the perceived roughness of product sounds (Bouter & Van Egmond, 2006). In the next step these sound events are related to experiential properties.

Concept and Sound Design Phase

Brand values of a company can be translated into experiential and functional properties. In this phase design concepts of sounds can be proposed that should evoke the required sound experience. First, an abstraction is made how the sound events develop over time. In Figure 6 the sound events are represent on a timeline. Similar sound events are presented on the same position vertically. This figure is an abstraction of Figure 5. It can be seen that the most complex sound production occurs after 50 seconds in which heating, pump, brew noise, and coffee all contribute to the sound experience.

Figure 6. Sound events of a coffemaker over time based on Figure 5.

The next step is to create a sound scenario in which the experience of the sound is described. In our example, a fast-boiler scenario was suggested with the condition that the sound evokes

the experience of quality, warmth, cosiness, and homely. In Figure 7 the sound events of this scenario are presented. The pump should run more regular and should start more gently than the original pump. This should result in a more pleasant sound. The sound of the pump was one of the main contributors to a negative evaluation of the sound (see above and later in the evaluation of pleasantness).

Figure 7. The sound events of a redesigned sound of a coffeemaker.

Normally more than one sound scenario is made that result in sound designs based on different experiential properties. The sound designs are then synthesized using recordings of sound producing parts, other parts than that are present in the current appliance, filtering techniques to simulate different damping or resonant aspects, and some physical modeling (for example, to simulate air flow). It is essential that these sound designs are based on realistic assumptions concerning the constructions. In this way, the sound designs can be translated into new suggestions to replace parts in the construction, the way parts are placed and connected in the construction or to “reprogram” the control system of the appliance. In the latter case one could think of not letting the pump start so abruptly. After these sound designs have been tested, they will be evaluated by people.

Evaluation Phase

In this phase original and/or newly designed sounds are evaluated. Two types of analysis methods are used. Rating scales are employed to evaluate the entire sound event or important parts of the sound event. In addition, the sound can be evaluated using an online measurement task. In this task the listener is asked while listening to a sound to rate on a scale how, for example, pleasant the sound is. Normally, a slider device consisting of a linear potentiometer is used that is sampled. The sound and the sampled rating data can then be mapped onto each other. This method allows to follow fluctuations in the perception over time. However, it

should be noted that especially experiences can be tracked that are related to the bottom-up process, experiences that are related to the top-down processing of sound events may not be that suited for continuous online tracking. The top-down process is probably more involved in percepts that are formed over a certain time period and these may be different than the sum of events in that time period. In the top part of Figure 8 the online rating on the pleasantness dimension of the original coffeemaker sound is presented as function of time. Each participant rated the sound on a continuous scale from 1 to 10 (1 being unpleasant and 10 being pleasant). The accumulation of the pleasantness scores over all participants is presented in pleasant categories (pleasant, fairly pleasant, neutral, fairly unpleasant, unpleasant). If many people rated something as unpleasant than the category is unpleasant indicated by the dark grey scale. In the bottom figure the sound events in time are shown. It can be readily seen that pump evokes a sense of unpleasantness.

Figure 8. Top figure: Accumulated pleasantness ratings as a function of time (in seconds). Bottom figure: The sound scenario of Figure 7.

In this way the experience of a sound can be tracked online. It enables one to relate people's judgment directly to the sound events. Consequently, the major trouble spots in the sound can be tracked in this way. On the basis of these evaluation choices can be made on which aspect to change the sound or to design new sounds on the basis of the evaluation.

Conclusion

The above methodology has been successfully applied in proposing new sound designs for coffeemakers, cleaning devices, and kitchen hoods. The advantage of this methodology is that realistic sounds are designed which are compliant to a company's brand values and to a required sound experience. However, the current methodology requires still a lot of craftsmanship of the person(s) who design(s) the sound. In addition, using recorded sound stemming from sound producing parts does not always allow systematic variations of the sound and is very time consuming. For the future we intend to incorporate more simulation and physical modeling techniques that allow us to manipulate sounds in a more controlled and systematic way. In addition, fundamental research into the perception and experience of product sounds will be conducted in order to gain more knowledge on the structural aspects of product sounds and on the type of product sounds. This work should allow us to define a product sound domain by sound categories that can be characterized by specific perceptual features and experiential attributes.

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